

Disease brief_West Nile Fever (WNF)

	Characteristics	Description
1	Disease and Pathogen	<p>West Nile fever is a mosquito-borne viral disease that can affect birds, humans and horses causing inapparent infection, mild febrile illness, meningitis, encephalitis, or death. Most people with febrile illness due to West Nile virus recover completely, but fatigue and weakness can last for weeks or months.</p> <p>West Nile virus (WNV) is a member of the genus <i>Flavivirus</i> in the family <i>Flaviviridae</i>. (1)</p>
2	Regulatory status in the EU	<p>WNF is listed in the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) Terrestrial Animal Health Code and must be reported by Members according to the WOAH Code. (2)</p> <p>WNF is listed in Regulation (EU) 2016/429, Reg (EU) 2018/1882, Reg (EU) 2020/2002</p> <p>WNV infections in humans and outbreaks in equids and birds are included in weekly updates during the WNV transmission season. (3)</p>
3	Geographical distribution (of autochthonous cases)	<p>WNV has a wide geographical range that includes parts of Europe, Asia, Africa, Australia and in North, Central and South America. [2] Since the beginning of the 2022 transmission season, 93 outbreaks among equids and 314 outbreaks among birds have been reported by EU/EEA countries: Outbreaks among equids have been reported by Italy, Germany, Greece, Croatia, Spain, France, Hungary, Portugal and Austria. Outbreaks among birds have been reported by Italy, Germany, Spain, Austria, Croatia and Hungary. (3) WOAH map is available – WAHIS Interface Platform about disease situation. Other maps available are: ECDC WNV dashboard, representing an updated overview about human and animal cases.</p>
4	Reservoir / main host	<p>The reservoir of the virus are birds. Most mammals do not develop enough virus in the bloodstream to spread the disease (their infection is incidental to the cycle in birds). The virus is maintained in a bird-mosquito cycle, with birds acting as amplifying hosts: mosquitoes acquire infection by feeding on viraemic birds. (1)</p>
5	Host range / susceptible species (domestic / wild)	<p>WNFV has a broad host range. It replicates in birds, reptiles, amphibians, mammals, mosquitoes and ticks. Susceptible are mainly wild birds: crows, jays and birds of prey. Humans and horses are considered dead end hosts. (1)</p>
6	Vector-borne transmission	<p>Transmitted by <i>Culex</i> genus mosquito bite (4): <i>Culex pipiens</i>, <i>perexiguus</i> and <i>molestus</i>, are important vectors susceptible to WNV infection and capable of transmission. (5)</p>

7	Environmental transmission	No.
8	(Main) transmission routes to domestic animals	Mosquito bite. The mosquitoes act as carriers (vectors) spreading the virus from an infected bird to other birds and to other animals. (2) Some species act as enzootic vectors (bird to bird), others as bridge vectors (bird to mammals).
9	(Main) transmission routes to humans	Mosquito bite. Transmission of WNV in humans occurred by blood transfusion, organ transplantation and breast milk, but most human infections occur by natural transmission from mosquitoes. Laboratory acquired infections have also been reported. (2)
10	Disease indicators	Disease that can affect birds, humans and horses causing inapparent infection, mild febrile illness, meningitis, encephalitis or death. (2)
11	a) Clinical signs	Fever, anorexia, and stiffness, central nervous system (CNS) dysfunction, and moderate to high mortality rates in horses (1). WNV encephalitis occurs in only a small percentage of infected horses; most infected horses do not display clinical signs. The disease in horses is frequently characterized by mild to severe ataxia, weakness, muscle fasciculation and cranial nerve deficits. Fever is an inconsistently recognized feature. The mortality rate is approximately one in three clinically affected unvaccinated horses. Most species of birds can become infected with WNV; the clinical outcome of infection is variable: some species appear resistant while others suffer fatal neurologic disease. In Europe fatal neurological disease has been reported in wild birds. (2)
	Shedding/detectability of pathogen	Equine WNV-specific IgM antibodies are usually detectable from 7–10 days post-infection (6)
12	b) Seroconversion	A low titer level viraemia may precede clinical onset. (6)
13	c) Other disease indicators	Not applicable.
14	Indicators relevant for monitoring (Indicator-based surveillance)	Fatal neurological disease reported in wild birds; high mortality rates of corvids and geese in an area. Neurological syndrome referable to encephalitis in horses. (2)
15	Test systems available for	<u>Identification of the agent:</u> In-vitro and in-vivo culture Specimens include brain (hindbrain and medulla) and spinal cord from deceased encephalitic horses; bird tissues including brain, heart or

	infection/disease detection	<p>liver may be used. WNV can also be isolated from mosquitoes. In general, virus isolates are obtained more easily from avian specimens. Test: Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)</p> <p><u>Serological Tests:</u> Antibodies can be identified in equine serum by IgM capture enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (IgM capture ELISA), haemagglutination inhibition (HI), IgG ELISA, plaque reduction neutralisation (PRN), and microtitre virus neutralisation (VN). The IgM capture ELISA is particularly useful for detecting equine antibodies resulting from recent natural exposure to WNV. The ELISA, HI, VN and PRN methods are most used for identifying WNV antibody in avian serum. The PRN test is the most specific among WNV serological tests; WN vaccination history must be considered in interpretation of serology results, particularly in the PRN and VN tests and IgG ELISA. The PRN test is applicable to any species, including birds. [2]</p>
16	Surveillance component options (+ rationale)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Clinical surveillance in Equidae (horses and donkeys) in endemic regions 2. Sentinel surveillance in chickens 3. Pathogen detection in wild birds with neurological symptoms or sudden death (caught or dead) 4. Pathogen detection in mosquitoes in endemic regions 5. Pathogen detection in mosquitoes in non-endemic regions bordering to endemic ones <p>WNV may pose a risk for endangered wildlife species in Europe. Among wild endangered species distributed in Europe potentially infected by West Nile virus (diagnosis includes direct detection of pathogen), classified according of their conservation status according (International Union for the Conservation of Nature), 34,7% species are "Near Threatened", 37,4% are "Vulnerable", 15,6% Endangered, and 12,2% Critically Endangered (CR) (14)</p>

		GENERAL POPULATION	EXPOSED	INFECTED	INFECTIOUS	SYMPTOMATIC	GP/VD VISIT	DEAD	Component name
VECTOR-borne diseases									
WEST NILE FEVER (WNF)	Equidae								Clinical surveillance in Equidae (horses and donkeys) in endemic areas
	Domestic birds								Sentinel surveillance in chickens
	Wild birds								Pathogen detection in wild birds with neurological symptoms or sudden death
	Mosquitoes								Pathogen detection in mosquitoes in endemic areas
									Pathogen detection in mosquitoes in non-endemic areas bordering to endemic ones
Human								Surveillance components targetting human were not in scope	

17	Comparison of surveillance component options (main advantages/disadvantages)	<p>1. Clinical surveillance in Equidae (horses and donkeys) in endemic regions – ADVANTAGES: system already recognized and standardized in several Mediterranean countries; allows to cover a large area of intervention; allows to investigate multiple diseases at the same time (e.g., Western, Eastern and Japanese encephalitis, Leishmania, Glanders, Rabies); research method already available and consolidated in MS where the disease is circulating; allows to study specific areas, in some cases not affected by the presence of sensitive avian species. DISADVANTAGES: the campaign must be managed by trained healthcare personnel; health risk for the operator who handles the animals</p> <p>2. Sentinel surveillance in chicken – ADVANTAGES: system already recognized and standardized in several Mediterranean countries; allows to focus on high-risk areas where adult female mosquitoes lay eggs on the surface of fresh or stagnant water on the outskirts of cities and population centres, bordering forests and wetlands; allows to investigate other diseases at the same time (e.g., HPAI); allows to identify the circulation of the infectious agent before human cases occur. DISADVANTAGES: resources needed for maintenance of sentinel flocks.</p> <p>3. Pathogen detection in wild birds with neurological symptoms or sudden death - ADVANTAGES: system already recognized and standardized in several Mediterranean countries;</p>
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		<p>allows to investigate other diseases at the same time (e.g., HPAI); allows to identify the circulation of the infectious agent before human cases occur. DISADVANTAGES: higher implementation costs compared to an ordinary sample collection campaign; requires a field follow-up of personnel with expertise in wild avian species.</p> <p>4. Pathogen detection in mosquitoes in endemic regions– ADVANTAGES: System already recognized and standardized in the main MS interested in the disease; it allows to cover a vast area of intervention; allows to investigate multiple diseases at the same time, e.g., Usutu virus (USUV), Rift Valley fever virus (RVFV), Japanese encephalitis virus (JEV), Sindbis virus (SINV); [4] Research method already available and consolidated at EU level. DISADVANTAGES: A large number of mosquitoes need to be collected to detect any virus; costs for trap specific for mosquitoes and of the field displacements to consider; pathogen detection in vectors is resource-intensive.</p> <p>5. Pathogen detection in mosquitoes in non-endemic regions bordering to endemic ones – ADVANTAGES: It allows to early detect changes in disease distribution; it allows to identify the spread of the disease before it manifests itself in the human species. DISADVANTAGES: A large number of mosquitoes need to be collected to detect any virus; costs for trap specific for mosquitoes and of the field displacements to consider; pathogen detection in vectors is resource-intensive.</p>
18	Countries which already carry out surveillance for this pathogen	<p>The data from WNV monitoring in animals is reported annually by EU countries under Directive 2003/99/EC [7] and presented in the annual The European Union One Health Zoonoses Report [8]. In Italy, a MS with one of the highest prevalence of the disease in human and animals in the EU [9], the National Plan for Prevention, Surveillance and Response to Arboviruses (PNA) 2020-2025 [10] combines human surveillance with veterinary and entomological surveillance. The surveillance is active year-round and enhanced during the transmission season, from the beginning of May to the end of November. The objective of the integrated surveillance for WNV is the early detection of virus circulation on the national territory during the vector activity season, by testing mosquitoes, birds, horses and humans, to reduce the risk of transmission to the latter. [11]</p>
19	References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) WOAH Terrestrial Manual Chapter 3.1.25. West Nile fever (version adopted in May 2018) 2) WOAH about disease – West Nile Fever, last updated 2022 3) Weekly updates: 2022 West Nile virus transmission season, last updated 15 Dec 2022 4) ECDC Culex pipiens - Factsheet for experts, last update 15 Jun 2020 5) Brugman VA, Hernández-Triana LM, Medlock JM, Fooks AR, Carpenter S, Johnson N. The Role of Culex pipiens L. (Diptera: Culicidae) in Virus Transmission in Europe. Int J Environ Res Public

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<https://www.cdc.gov/westnile/symptoms/index.html#:~:text=About%201%20in%205%20people,symptoms%20in%20a%20few%20people>.
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20	Additional comments	<p>Animal data (including outbreaks among equids and birds) are collected through the Animal Disease Information System (ADIS) of the European Commission and regular summaries are available online. [3] Prevalence data in animals are available on WAHIS Interface data research platform. Since the beginning of the 2022 transmission season and as of 23 November 2022, EU/EEA countries have reported 965 human cases of WNV infection in Italy (586), Greece (284), Romania (46), Hungary (14), Germany (11), Croatia (8), Austria (6), Spain (5), France (4) and Slovakia (1). EU/EEA countries have reported 73 deaths in Italy (37), Greece (31) and Romania (5). EU-neighbouring countries have reported 226 human cases of WNV infection in Serbia (226) and 12 deaths in Serbia (12). (3)</p>
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